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Review Article

Evaluating Lumbar Disc Degeneration by MRI Quantitative Metabolic Indicators: The Perspective of Factor Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Lumbar disc degeneration (LDD) is a prevalent condition affecting millions worldwide, often leading to debilitating pain and a reduced quality of life. While MRI remains a crucial diagnostic tool for LDD, there's a growing interest in leveraging quantitative metabolic indicators to enhance assessment accuracy. Factor analysis offers a novel perspective by identifying underlying metabolic factors contributing to LDD progression. This review examines recent advancements in MRI-based metabolic assessments, emphasizing the potential of factor analysis in elucidating the complex interplay of metabolic markers associated with LDD. Insights gained from this analysis could revolutionize LDD diagnosis, prognosis, and therapeutic strategies, ultimately improving patient outcomes. Lumbar disc degeneration (LDD) is a prevalent condition affecting millions worldwide, often leading to debilitating pain and a reduced quality of life. While MRI remains a crucial diagnostic tool for LDD, there's a growing interest in leveraging quantitative metabolic indicators to enhance assessment accuracy. Factor analysis offers a novel perspective by identifying underlying metabolic factors contributing to LDD progression. This review examines recent advancements in MRI-based metabolic assessments, emphasizing the potential of factor analysis in elucidating the complex interplay of metabolic markers associated with LDD. Insights gained from this analysis could revolutionize LDD diagnosis, prognosis, and therapeutic strategies, ultimately improving patient outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

The leading cause of low back pain is lumbar disc degeneration, which is the focus of both surgical and diagnostic procedures [1]. One of the most prevalent musculoskeletal complaints is low

back pain (LBP), which is thought to be the cause of 2.8% to 5% of US doctor visits, with a higher percentage occurring in younger individuals with fewer chronic medical issues [2-3].

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There are numerous elements that are involved with this illness. The disc itself is a living tissue with important self-healing mechanisms [4]. When taking into account both direct expenditures and indirect costs, like lost wages and productivity, the total cost of LBP exceeds \$100 billion annually in the United States alone [5]. Generally, by the second decade of life, lumbar spine disc degeneration starts sooner in life than the degradation of any other connective tissue in the human body [6-9]. The intervertebral disc (IVD) loses its ability to effectively absorb physiological loads as degeneration advances. This causes load transfer to neighboring vertebral bodies, which can result in end plate alterations, the production of osteophytes, and trabecular microfractures [10]. Discograms, however, probably reveal a lot about the intervertebral disc's state of degeneration; after all, they are patterns that show how radio-opaque fluid is injected into a disc, and this distribution must be dependent on the nucleus's physical characteristics as well as the annulus's fissures. Based on characteristics in the shape and density of the radio-opaque shadow that were consistently recognizable, different types of discograms were identified. Only five of these discogram types were found to correspond to different stages of disc degeneration when the discograms and the disc slices were thoroughly compared. Among the five discogram kinds are, 1. Cotton ball 2. Lobular 3. Irregular 4. Fissured 5. Ruptured. No signs of degeneration. (1) COTTON BALL: The radio-opaque shadow has a homogeneous density and seems to be confined within the nucleus. There were no symptoms of degradation on these discs. In non-injected specimens, the nucleus was a soft, white, amorphous gel without any fibrous lumps or cracks, while the annulus was white and smooth. (2) LOBULAR: The radio-opaque shadow has a lobular appearance, appearing to be contained within the nucleus. It is denser in the vicinity of the

end-plates and less dense or nonexistent in the center. Common shapes are horseshoe-shaped or hamburger-shaped. (3) IRREGULAR: The radio-opaque shadow appears to pierce the inner annulus and has an irregular form. There were clear indications of degradation on these discs. features clefts and tiny fissures in the inner annulus and nucleus, as well as a fibrous nucleus. The nucleus and annulus were not well distinguished from one another. (4) FISSURED: No contrast material escapes from the disc through the annulus, but the radio-opaque shadow is visible on the discogram stretching to the outer margin of the annulus (perhaps beyond the edge of the vertebral body. (5) RUPTURED: The discogram displays contrast material that completely exits the disc and extends to the annulus' periphery [11]. In the lumbar spine, there are several possible sources of pain, but symptomatic disc degeneration is considered to be a major cause of low back pain (LBP) [12,13]. and makes up more than 25% of lumbar fusion surgeries conducted in the US[3] Recent years have seen a significant focus on the molecular underpinnings of degenerative disc degeneration, which has substantially improved our knowledge of the biology behind this process. Stepwise cascades of altered IVD production of degradative enzymes, inflammatory cytokines, and extracellular matrix (ECM) result in the end-stage morphological abnormalities observed on routine clinical imaging examinations [14].

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY:

The fluid and proteoglycan content of the lumbar disc are associated with its strength. By attracting water into the nucleus pulposus by osmosis, the hydrophilic property of proteoglycan and the negative charge on the branched chains internally pressurize the disc. Regrettably, as we age, the disc's water content and proteoglycan levels tend to decline [15-19]. Research has indicated that applied stress causes the disc to degenerate; however, the exact mechanism is yet unknown.

Genetics may have a role in disc degeneration; Sahlman et al.,[20]. The cartilaginous VB endplate's capillary beds offer the majority of the disc nutrition [21]. Schmorl nodes occur as a result of cartilaginous endplate disruption [22]. The vascular alterations could be connected to the ingrowth of arteries from osteophyte development and happen prior to the degenerative process [23]. One of the most common proteoglycans in the body is collagen. While Type II and IX collagen are reported to be enhanced in areas of moderate degeneration but absent in areas of more advanced illness, Type I collagen is detected in the nucleus pulposus and annulus fibrosis in both normal and pathologically deteriorated discs [24]. It has been demonstrated that N-(carboxymethyl) lysine, a marker of oxidative stress linked to alteration of the collagen protein structure, rises with the progression of degenerative illness [25]. Reduced pyridinoline crosslinks result in changes to the disc's collagen matrix. Aging is linked to pentosidine levels in the disc. Patients over 65 had pyridinoline concentrations that were almost 50% higher than those of younger patients [26]. Both healthy and diseased conditions experience apoptosis, which is planned cell death. Uncertainty surrounds the function of apoptosis in lumbar disc degeneration [27]. Fibronectin concentrations in degenerated discs are higher than usual; this may be an effect of the body responding to damage [28]. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that mechanical stress raises MMPs 2 and 9 activity in articular cartilage, indicating a rise in tissue turnover that may damage the disc [29]. Additionally observed in herniated discs are increases in MMPs, NO, PGE-2, and IL-6 [30]. Herniation is believed to be the consequence of an annulus fibrosis defect, most likely brought on by the disc being subjected to extreme stress [31]. Most frequently, a herniation happens on the disc's posterolateral or posterior surfaces [32]. The extruded section always contains material from the

nucleus pulposus, regardless of the source of the tear, according to histological assessment [33]. Protrusions are focal areas of extension that are still connected to the disc, while disc bulges are symmetrical extensions of the disc outside of the endplates [34,35].

MRI TECHNIQUES FOR QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS:

The method used most frequently to assess IVD in both healthy and deteriorating states is magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [36]. Axial T2-weighted, sagittal T1-weighted spin-echo, and T2-weighted spin-echo pictures are examples of standard MRI sequences [37]. MRIs can be quantitatively measured to determine specific tissue parameters associated with pathological alterations, or they can be qualitatively evaluated to describe the morphology of deteriorated IVDs [38]. One useful method for quantitatively and noninvasively evaluating the composition, integrity, and biomechanics of the disc matrix is quantitative magnetic resonance imaging (qMRI) [39]. Nucleus pulposus (NP) size, hydration, and proteoglycan content are the most pertinent parameters in intervertebral discs (IVD) for quantitative evaluations because of their declines, which are important aspects of the disc degeneration process [38]. To link MRI signals to disc tissue ratio (MTR), and the apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC). Both matrix integrity (percentage of collagen denaturation) and IVD matrix composition (water, proteoglycan, and collagen) have an impact on qMRI parameters (T1, T2, T1rho, MTR, and ADC) [39].

With disc degeneration, disc herniation, and water loss, the T1 relaxation constant falls [40]. Another basic MR characteristic is T2 relaxation; T2 values correlate with the disc's water and proteoglycan levels, causing T2 to drop when those contents are lost. In disc degeneration, it has been applied to determine NP hydration [38,40]. In quantitative MRI analysis, T1rho (time constant of transverse

magnetization decay) is a valuable statistic that mostly corresponds with the compressive characteristics and water content of the disc. T1rho has been linked to discogenic pain and decreases with water and proteoglycan loss. Proteoglycans and other slowly moving macromolecules in the NP have been assessed using T1rho methods, which measure transverse relaxation in the presence of a spin-locking pulse [41-43]. Another potential marker for the identification of IDD is the apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) from diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI), which reflects changes in the content of the nucleus pulposi matrix indirectly [44]. Systems of morphologic grading have been developed to assess the appearance and degree of IVD degeneration that can be seen on standard magnetic resonance imaging. IVDs are graded from 1 (normal) to 5 (total collapse) using the Pfirrmann grading system, which considers disc structure, signal intensity, and disc height in sagittal T2-weighted spin echo images [45,46]. While T2-weighted imaging (T2WI)-based grading systems are especially useful for determining the degeneration in later stages, the Pfirrmann score system offers a semi-quantitative assessment of IDD in vivo [47]. In order to detect and quantify composition, structure, and biomechanical changes to the human IVD, qMRI can be utilized as a noninvasive diagnostic technique. As a result, it has the potential to be a crucial diagnostic and therapy assessment tool for figuring out the disc's functioning condition [48].

CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS:

Significant clinical consequences result from lumbar disc degeneration, which is typically characterized by radiculopathy (compression of the nerve roots), reduced mobility, and persistent lower back discomfort. Patients may have worsening symptoms as the condition worsens, such as spinal stenosis and disc herniation, which can result in neurological impairments and

functional impairment. A multidisciplinary approach is frequently used in management, involving physical therapy, pain management, and, in extreme situations, surgical intervention. To maximize patient outcomes and reduce long-term disability, early diagnosis via imaging and focused therapies are essential.

FUTURE DIRECTION:

In the upcoming years, lumbar disc degeneration research is expected to progress in a number of areas. First off, customized medicine is receiving more attention. It uses genetic and biomarker data to customize therapies for each patient. Better results and more effective interventions may result from this. Furthermore, developments in regenerative medicine have the potential to replace or repair damaged discs, providing patients with long-term remedies. Additionally, attempts are being made to enhance longevity, lessen problems, and broaden the range of applications for artificial disc technology. Additionally, there is growing interest in non-surgical methods that may be very beneficial in controlling symptoms and delaying the course of the disease, such as focused physical therapy, pain management strategies, and lifestyle changes. Treatment planning and diagnostic accuracy may be improved by incorporating state-of-the-art imaging modalities including functional imaging and sophisticated MRI techniques. Lastly, to drive innovation and translate scientific discoveries into clinical practice, interdisciplinary collaboration among orthopedic surgeons, neurosurgeons, radiologists, engineers, and researchers from other domains will be critical.

FACTOR ANALYSIS:

By offering deeper insights into the data and assisting in the accuracy of medical diagnoses, factor analysis can be integrated into MRI evaluation to greatly improve the capabilities of MRI. But for it to be implemented successfully, one must have a solid grasp of the statistical techniques at play as well as the clinical context of

the MRI results. It is anticipated that the use of these analytical approaches in MRI will grow in frequency and sophistication as technology and methods progress.

CONCLUSION:

This study utilizes quantitative metabolic indicators derived from MRIs to evaluate lumbar disc degeneration using factor analysis. The outcomes provide significant insight into the multifaceted nature of degeneration by identifying specific metabolic elements that result in it. This improves clinical management techniques and makes therapeutic interventions more accurate. Although QMRI has significant potential, more technological advancements are required to make it possible to utilize it in clinical settings, analyze and detect IVD degeneration early, and assess the efficacy of regenerative therapies.

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